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EXTREME SURGICAL CONTEXTS THE PERSPECTIVE OF INDUSTRIAL DESIGN ENGINEERING

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ABSTRACT

Healthcare has an increasing presence in the agenda of both design practice and design research. In the particular case of surgical care, the specialized products designed to be used in advanced operating rooms (OR), sometimes have specific characteristics that do not allow for proper functioning in poor-resourced settings or in contexts of emergencies such as natural disasters. Diverse literature identifies barriers to healthcare and medical device innovation that are relevant for designers and ought to be considered throughout all product development process. In this paper, the reviewed contextual barriers to the use of medical devices are translated into examples of design relevant interventions. From business approaches to technical details, design engineering practice has within its domain the potential to overcome some barriers. Most importantly this research attempts to contribute to the practice of design by 1) enriching existing literature about methodological approaches to design for complex contexts and 2) creating an information platform that supports the stakeholders involved in the development of surgical equipment, designing more context adequate products.

Keywords: Research-by-design; Surgical design engineering; Barriers to emergency surgery.

INTRODUCTION

Emergency surgery is defined by the curative solution for an acute problem, urgent disease or injury that threatens a patient's life.

In opposition to elective surgery, an emergency must be performed immediately and, besides the orthopaedic speciality, mostly open surgery (although in some cases of appendicitis or hernias minimal invasive approaches) is used. The context of emergency surgery is very heterogeneous and not standardized worldwide (Razzak & Kellermann 2002; Catena & Moore 2007).

An emergency surgery does not necessarily mean the procedure is any different than an elective one. What differs is the time frame between diagnosis and operation. Normally every surgical procedure integrates a team of different specialists that allow the performance of all the phases of care: from diagnosis using observation to radiology, preparation for operation (mainly nursing work), and operating under monitored anaesthesia where two or more surgeons - generally a chief surgeon and an assistant - a scrub nurse and a circulating nurse perform all the tasks of instruments handling. Following any surgery there is a recovery phase called post-operative phase, normally occurring in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) and a follow up or rehabilitation phase under advice of a specialist doctor (Pezzella 2006).

For the purpose of this paper, extreme context refers to the opposite of these "normal" settings, characteristics that justify its difficulty and even hindrance of care by lengthening the time of practice and reducing its safety (of patient and provider) and quality. These factors also characterize the difference between two extremes of the world: the developed and the developing.

DISASTERS AND DEVELOPMENT

The world experiences an increasing frequency and severity of disaster emergencies: from major earthquakes, nuclear accidents and conflicts. In addition to those, urbanization and population growth represent a serious threat to political, economic and social stability (Joint UNEP/OCHA Environment Unit 2009). The context of developing countries and of one billion citizens that cohabit in disaster-prone regions (Ryan 2005) - "where an estimated 97% of worldwide natural disaster-related deaths occur every year" - is characterized by a set of factors which makes populations more vulnerable to impact and limit them to develop. Isolation from information, healthcare, and education; the lack of mobility and infrastructures; the unplanned housing and environmental degradation; and very weak public health systems are some of these factors. The technological and informational unpreparedness together with dysfunctional health systems leads to the devastation of resources of a population and their recovery capacity. So besides the destruction of goods, services and infrastructures lives are lost making it impossible for a population to recover and develop. There are several on-going discussions about the unsustainable dependency on foreign aid of these nations and the existing gap between humanitarian relief and necessary development programs (Bureau for Crisis Prevention and Recovery 2004).

DEVELOPMENT AND SURGERY

Emergency surgery is one of the most essential services for disaster relief due to the amount of sudden injuries that threaten a population. Worldwide, and in particular in developing countries, this service is often understood as an immoderate and costly solution. However, its cost effectiveness was proven by examples such as foreign intervention for birth complications, trauma and congenital abnormalities. There is a growing recognition of surgical care as a valuable investment for quality public health as it can respond effectively to emergencies, contributing to the reduction of deaths and disabilities and strengthening the capacity of societal development (Musgrove & Fox-Rushby 2006; Luboga et al. 2009; Ivers et al. 2008) (Kushner et al. 2010). The characteristics of a natural disaster relief

operation where international and national organizations like the Médecins Sans Frontières respond to the needs of innumerable victims are somewhat comparable to the often reported resource-poor conditions of surgical care in developing countries. When a disaster strikes in a developing region, such as Haiti (Earthquake, 2010) surgery becomes more challenging.

The first 48 to 72 hours are crucial for victims with life-threatening injuries. This requires a quick response of local professionals and requires international relief agencies to organize logistics, deploy and set-up temporary "out of context" operating rooms (OR). Afterwards all patients are firstly submitted to a triage, where patients with most urgency and the best chance of survival are chosen and then prepared for surgery. Until the following 10 days priority surgery is performed. The post-operative and reconstruction surgery phase is required for months after the event (Malish et al. 2009). Quick response of international relief agencies is often obstructed due to governmental constraints or climate instability and so local professionals have a beneficial position. However, few technologies succeed to adapt to such settings. Factors as the poorly distributed income and shortage of urban-rural mobility infrastructures remain serious threats to development of specialized care to treat disability. Some studies describe the inequity of access to the most basic technology (Pearson & Shoo 2005; Currat et al. 2004). It is estimated that around 100 billion €/year are spent globally on medical research and development (R&D) of which only 10% belongs to health problems of 90% of the world population. Literature reveals a recent intention to establish care priorities for surgical disease burden, from procedure and missions' cost effectiveness studies to needs assessment studies and reports of experiences with training programs (Mock et al. 2010; Debas et al. 2006). Yet, there is still limited capacity to assess the different environmental conditions of surgical practice worldwide in a systematic manner.

The heterogeneous character of the existing literature reveals that this limited capacity happens due to the variety of surgical specializations and pathologies and the worldwide variation of infrastructure, minimum standards and best

practices assessments (K. a K. McQueen et al. 2009; Nickerson 2011).

PROBLEM DEFINITION

The identified barriers to surgical care in low-income countries show a large evidence of the scarcity of adequate medical devices (Grimes et al. 2011). The World Health Organization (WHO) published several reports reflecting on the problematic around the drive of medical devices development and the questionable utility of some technology innovation for public health. Surgical equipment and medical technology are largely targeted at high-income countries and under the stimulus of better, more sophisticated solutions. They are developed to function in a controlled clean environment and so characteristics, such as environment austerity (dust, heat and humidity) and poor infrastructures (road, buildings, electricity) represent big time conditioning to proper use and maintenance of products. The available equipment in poor-resourced regions is largely donated, but unused and/or not repaired. Incomplete, incompatible or unreliable equipment affects the outcome of the procedure by endangering patient or staff and extending the time and/or surgical procedural steps. Emergency surgery often implies working at night, having a high degree of variance between adults and children, particular safety requirements and guidelines, few time to operate, and high demand from patients. The challenge of developing such specialized surgical equipment is that many factors must be considered, e.g., particular safety requirements, sub-system dependency, maintenance and durability. Besides these there are some barriers to their implementation, such as the learning curve, standards and certification and different institutional protocols as well as different knowledge of doctors (Giannou & Baldan 2009; World Health Organization 2010).

STATE OF THE ART

The intervention of design engineering (Roozemburg & Eekels 1995) in the field of medical devices innovation has been developing over the recent years with a user centred approach to technology and with the collaboration of many different clients, from hospitals to companies.

Through participative methodologies of inquiry and iterative design cycles, devices come closer to the desires and understanding of their users and health-related safety increases (Clemensen et al. 2007; Wauben et al. 2011; Melles 2011; Jalote-Parmar et al. 2007).

The research project presented in this paper uses a combination of research and design, where the results of the research based design is used as a source of new knowledge, accountable to new design cycles. The process considers the product-service system framework developed within eco-design approach, which focuses on the dematerialization of products into services or product-service systems (Horvath 2007; Crul et al. 2009). The same approach is based on the consideration of the complete life-cycle of a product during the design process and on the analysis of the product's impact in the three distinct elements of sustainability: economic, social, and environment for value creation.

OBJECTIVES

The aim of this paper is to create a sound starting point for the development of guidelines for context-centred surgical devices design in extreme contexts. This goal is defined under the assumption that developing context adequate surgical technology (and associated methodologies) contributes to a more sustainable transfer of instruments used by humanitarian relief teams.

METHODS

A general online literature search was conducted about emergency surgery in resource-poor settings in common databases and websites (e.g., Google, World Health Organization, United Nations). The search included diverse documents types (e.g., journal articles, institutional websites, field reports), iterating through synonyms, references and citations over the last ten years. Additionally, information was obtained during the participation in the "Surgical Issues" working group from the 2011 Humanitarian Action Summit and by conducting unstructured interviews with different experts involved with surgery and the humanitarian field.

The outcomes include (1) quantitative information about the global burden of surgical disease in extreme contexts, priority procedures and

equipment,(2) an overview of contextual barriers involved in surgical care based on diverse literature, and (3) a table with the elaborated design engineering considerations regarding the mentioned barriers. An additional remark in this paper is a set of assumptions for product development priorities. Finally a first approximation to design guidelines elaborated from this study is provided. These assumptions, derived from the three previously described results, were confirmed to be priority issues by conducting separate unstructured discussions to healthcare professionals with field experience. They will be explored further using a research-based design approach and make use of the discussion points that follow.

RESULTS

GLOBAL BURDEN OF SURGICAL DISEASE

In order to understand the role of equipment in the surgery context and establish guidelines for improved development, it is necessary to know the need for surgical care in developing countries and know which patterns and priorities exist in disaster situations. In the book “Disease Control Priorities in Developing Countries” from the World Bank it is estimated that diseases treatable with surgery represent 11% of the global burden of disease (GBD). Within this 11% there are different types of problems. Injury for instance accounts for 38% of these surgical cases in the world (Debas et al. 2006).

Severe injuries account for 10% of worldwide deaths/year (1-2 million), 90% of which occur in developing countries (K. McQueen et al. 2010). Future predictions even expect an increase in the frequency of injuries by 2030 classifying them as worldwide leading disability causes. (WHO 2011). Of an estimated 234 million surgical procedures done every year, the wealthiest third of the global population has 75% of the operations, whereas the poorest third undergoes only 4% (Funk et al. 2010). The fact that the latter bear the greatest burden of morbidity and mortality indicates a substantial unmet need for surgical care. Few data though, exists about the burden of unmet surgical disease (K. M. Chu et al. 2010).

Disasters cause different types of problems depending on their type intensity. However, there

are common injuries such as limb fractures, soft tissue wounds and severe infections caused by the collapse of structures, penetrating debris and dirty environment. So most humanitarian missions in rescue of the affected populations belong to the general, orthopaedic and vascular field. What is verifiable though is that the remainder of surgical needs of a population, the non-disaster related problems like obstetric complications and problems like disfiguring hernias, club feet and cleft lip are operated in more quantity by the humanitarian teams (K. McQueen et al. 2010).

Each medical speciality has determined and specific equipment needs, but there are common items within all surgical specialities (Ryan 2005). All surgical patients need stabilization of their body condition and require oxygen and intravenous (IV) fluids. Wounds and fractures require cleaning and most crushed limbs will undergo a specific repair (fasciotomy) and/or an amputation with specific tools. Some treatments are not considered surgical care but have a direct link, e.g., the case of dialysis for cases of extreme blood loss, and prosthesis which must have proper limb length for application (Mock et al. 2010; Li et al. 2009).

The World Health Organization, the International committee of the Red Cross and Médecins Sans Frontières developed clinical and technical guidelines dedicated to surgery and anaesthesia in disasters or humanitarian crisis that can be used as a basis by other organizations (World Health Organization 2007; Giannou & Balcan 2009). Some particular authors and associations also propose lists of minimum requirements for humanitarian surgery (Pezzella 2006) (Owens et al. 2005). Standards and packaging requirements are evident concerns although for most the selection criteria and requirements elaboration is unclear. Few references were found about availability assessment or research of a specific instrument (Myles & Haller 2010).

CONTEXTUAL BARRIERS IN SURGICAL CARE

The contextual characteristics were collected from two recent literature reviews concerning the impediments to emergency surgical care (Grimes et al. 2011) and to the implementation of medical devices in developing countries (Petkova 2010).

These two studies were complemented with the knowledge gathered from the further research made about the topic (Levine et al. 2007; Dankelman 2010; Dewo et al. 2008; Malkin 2007; Solomon 2002; Manley et al. 2006).

The mentioned barriers were grouped in Table 1 and divided in four groups according to an adaptation of a multilevel design model (Joore 2010). In this model, context is divided into scales of design intervention throughout time.

So in this case, the societal system will be the "policies" level, the socio-technical system will be "environment" level, the functional product-service system will be "knowledge" and the operational product-technology system, "equipment". Each of these systems or levels have a determined cycle of innovation (the design process) and is ordered by a decreasing time of development of each intervention, being that an intervention in the societal system takes longer than in the systems below.

Policy
There are many administrative and financial barriers related with surgical care. Amongst them are costs of care and transportation and indirect costs of adopting and maintaining technology which contrast with the low income and poor quality of life of populations. In addition, the absence of management capabilities affects the distribution of services (e.g., not admitting patients with low status or no communication amongst departments) and resources (e.g., shipping delays or border restrictions).
Environment
Different environment characteristics affect surgical care both of infrastructure or services. Most become particularly severe in a disaster situation. Infrastructure is mostly poor and disrupted and this includes not only facilities and equipment but also the unreliable electrification and road access. In a disaster, climate instability, stifling air, humidity and dust are true threats for surgery and surgeons. Surgical procedures are also held up due to the lack of staff, the insecurity and time pressure caused by the intense affluence of patients and variance of adult and children.

Knowledge
The cultural aspects of a certain population can represent a constrain for surgery provision (e.g., religious believes) and communication-related issues (e.g., language and genre inequality). Experience factors of the population (e.g., awareness, fear), of the medical staff (e.g., no education, different practices) or with technology (e.g., less exposure to technology, learning curve, lack of manuals) are also fundamental for the proper servicing of surgery.
Equipment
Administrative and technical aspects of equipment represent a smaller scale, but not less severe, of challenges. Poor administration of incoming and existing equipment (e.g., payment modality, stock control), difficulty of testing prototypes (discussed in detail further) and no life-cycle support services (e.g., supply chain, repair, disposal) hinder the subsistence of any equipment. Further administrative issues are the dependence on a source of consumables' supply, sometimes outdated or not accepted due to being locally produced. In the technical level, materials, portability, vulnerability, dependency on human labour, components (e.g. cables) or servicing (e.g. calibration, repair tools) make surgical devices very prone to be broken, dirty, incompatible and unsafe to use. In disaster settings energy and water dependency are subjected to shortages which means no sterilization and no functioning of devices, thus no surgical care.

Table 1. Overview of contextual barriers in policy, environment, communication and engineering levels

DESIGN ENGINEERING CONSIDERATIONS

An integrated approach

Design has been acknowledged for contributing to the safety improvement in healthcare environments (Clarkson et al. 2003). The design related problems describe the perspective of an industrial design engineer on the information collected about contextual conditions of surgery in developing countries and disasters. The suggestions are divided into three levels of design interventions, each

dependent on specific methodological approaches to address the problems of contextual barriers: Strategic, Communication and Engineering.

All the proposed interventions are related with how medical devices can be designed, from innovative concepts to incremental re-designs, in order to overcome contextual barriers.

The strategic level interventions are meant to describe new concepts of business where products are used. Designers can innovate at this level through the decomposition of a problem like “technology adoption costs” into smaller problems like “maintenance technician” or “supply of consumables” which can be later translated into adjacent services or value to products (Tukker & Tischner 2006).

The communication level of interaction design can address knowledge contextual barriers with user-centred products like e.g., embedded instruction cues, symbols of repair steps or platforms for awareness raising (IDEO 2009).

The engineering level of interaction is the most technical level of interventions that addresses the relationship between environmental and equipment barriers. Approaches like contextual design, life-cycle design and modular design are adequate tools to investigate how product features influence the work of users and their environment throughout time (Beyer & Holtzblatt 1998; Brezet & van Hemel 1997). This paper is addressed at designers, manufacturers, donors and other healthcare professionals who handle medical equipment and to which the extent of awareness about the barriers in these contexts might be limited (Levine et al. 2007).

Table 2 provides an overview of design engineering relevant issues, divided into the three dimensions of design thinking: Strategy, Communication and Engineering. These three are intrinsically related and all can enrich the capabilities of medical devices to be best adequate to what’s required from them.

Interaction Design: Universal language for knowledge transfer and support information
Engineering
Technical Design: Product characteristics and ergonomics, consolidation of components and energy self-sufficiency

Table 2. Overview of design engineering relevant issues

Some ways how design can make a positive change, adding value to surgical devices, are listed and clarified in the table below, under the same division of intervention levels.

Strategy
Strategic models applied to products help companies to find opportunities which fit their visions and position them in competitive advantage. Through Product-Service-System Design it is possible to involve all stakeholders in finding integrated solutions that have the potential to self-evolve from free services to economic independence. Suggestions however, are not to generalize but serve simply as illustrative examples. Accessibility businesses include lease or pool services (e.g., transportation, sterilization, laboratories), adaptation of medical basic kits to public vehicles and arrangements with local entities for manufacturing, supply and distribution shares. Knowledge transfer in training, supply and disposal services built-in device concepts are opportunities for design innovation. Arrangements between manufacturer and technical school to share a degree (for device technicians) or supporting local community for basic life support learning (e.g. India Institute of Technology manual). Local supply or design alternatives can circumvent prohibition at international border (International Narcotics Control Board) and take back waste service with deposit money reduces the danger of incorrect reuse of contagious products. Indirect added value can be found in smart products embedded with feedback sensors (e.g., temperature control blood bags) and built in drives for calibration. These replace the need for extra devices and specialized staff. Kits also reduce the need to search for loose equipment and instructions

Strategy
Product-Service-System Design: Business models for accessibility, support knowledge transfer and add indirect value to products
Communication

<p>and can offer different configurations for different users preferences, capabilities and possibilities.</p>	<p>positive. Equipment can play a role when defending the staff involved in an operation by considering the material use in personal safety equipment (e.g., lightweight, resistance to wear, waterproof, efficacy of wash), auto-disabling functions (e.g., Star Syringe), shapes that can promote cleanness and safety (e.g., avoiding grooves, double injection plastics) and grouping of necessary components (e.g., electro-cautery ground plate) to avoid forgetting their application.</p> <p>Consolidation of components in a device is relevant for the ergonomics and ease of use. Stackable and modular principles, integrating functions and being easy to disassemble without particular tools (from carcass to circuit printed boards) can improve the performance of products throughout their life-cycle. Other interventions, such as reducing packaging and increasing self-contained products, reducing also the amount of moving parts and components (e.g., replacement parts, cables, accessories) also contribute to good functioning. Lightweight and resilience is very important in disaster settings.</p> <p>Materials and device configurations should be taken in account (e.g., difficult to repair broken plastic, unstable wheels).</p> <p>Energy self-sufficiency is required for e.g., equipment functioning, sterilization and illumination. The most common solution of mobile energy is the use of fuel driven generators. The fact that fuel is (reaching its peak) a consumable makes energy dependent on a temporary supply chain vulnerable to interruptions and by-passing. Possible solutions include reducing energy consumption of devices and dependency from batteries (or, from supply of) or develop bi-mode devices with a manual mode for energy shortages.</p>
<p>Communication</p>	
<p>Communication is inherent to a product through embedded use cues or independent formats helping the user understand the product, its function or simply how to interact with it. Interaction Design focuses on an effective interaction between people and amongst people and devices which is fundamental for the reduction of time and errors during surgery related events.</p> <p>Knowledge transfer can be facilitated underlining a structure with an universal language different users can understand. Examples are embedded information (in device) about function and cost-effectiveness as well as needed infrastructure and equipment management.</p> <p>Support information is needed in many different scales and applications. From community awareness, training manuals through clinical guidelines and mediators like peri-operative drawings and record keeping; triage facilitation through identification of patients and establishment of rules; Informed consent ethics and follow up instructions for families and finally instructions and labels of products by using different intuitive supports (e.g., digital, video) and facilitating storage and reading.</p>	
<p>Engineering</p>	<p><i>Table 3. Design Engineering Relevant issues in the design of surgical equipment for extreme contexts</i></p> <p>ASSUMPTIONS FOR FURTHER DEVELOPMENT</p> <p>In the sequence of an iterative process of topic-based search in field reports and journal articles, a set of assumptions about the fields with potential to explore further were gathered.</p> <p>From the literature the life-saving potential and clinical priority of instruments were established and confronted with the industrial design scale and a</p>
<p>From the engineering perspective there are key technical factors that account for the product's usability and proper functioning in context. Developing technologies adequate for developing countries does not necessarily imply "low-price low-tech, low quality". The development for resource-poor contexts and the opportunity for them of leapfrogging (as it happened with telephone technology) should be regarded as an opportunity to develop more sustainable equipment, under the innovation perspective that they can be imported and used by developed countries.</p> <p>Product characteristics such as shape, dimensions and materials contribute significantly for the safety of medical devices. Safety of staff is threatened by Hepatitis, Tuberculosis and in particular HIV so it is a common practice to assume all patients are</p>	

desired fast development time factors (Mock et al. 2010). Table 4 describes the elaborated assumptions.

Sterilization and maintenance
Regarding the fact that sterilization is fundamental at all stages of surgical care for debridement of wounds, operating and cleaning of instruments, the current need to transport sterilization solutions or chlorine pastilles in large amounts and in small capacity bottles seems dramatic. Autoclaves often require energy, are slow and bulky for large orthopaedic instruments. Solutions should mainly address the packaging/labelling, the transport/borders and disposal issues.
Anaesthesia
Stabilization of injured patients and pregnancy complications has proven to be problematic in several cases. Once again supply and transport are an issue since these packages are not designed to operate in extreme contexts. Oxygen availability is still non-existent in several settings. Transporting oxygen represents still a burden for humanitarian teams due to the energy demand of oxygen concentrators, weight and hazard of oxygen bottles.
Surgery
Two simple but important devices during a surgical procedure are: illumination and electrocautery. Both can reduce the time of a procedure and exhaustion of a surgeon. Electrocautery is an interesting alternative to supply intensive needles and sutures, it revokes the need of stitches removal and risk of haemorrhage. These two represent the interesting logistic challenge of energy efficiency in resource-poor environments.

Table 4. Assumptions for further development

DISCUSSION

In this paper a relation between natural disasters, societal development and (emergency) surgery was made to illustrate the unmet need of emergency surgical care in developing countries. There are clear problems related with medical devices and their appropriateness to operate in settings other than the ones they were designed for. These same devices are nevertheless used in austere settings. Throughout

this paper the barriers to surgical care provision and innovation were analysed from a general perspective of design engineering. The literature on surgical care in developing countries and the barriers it faces is recent and rarely systematic.

This study intended to demonstrate the scope of possible interventions of design to contribute positively for the adequacy of technology in this field.

Designing products for healthcare and in particular for OR presents particular challenges for both the designer and the researcher. The complex interrelation of activities and devices in these environments difficult the collection of information. Furthermore, it is a context of unpredictability, diversity of conditions and very specific knowledge and language. Designing products for healthcare that can operate in the extreme settings poses a number of additional specific challenges namely due to the practice focus of most humanitarian organizations. In a disaster context, time, space and research related ethics are additional concerns. Hand in hand with research is prototyping and the challenge of testing solutions in a realistic setting. Another point, is the fact that the most recent development of devices for developing countries is based on ideas generated in developed countries rather than within them (Beenkens & Stolk 2010). The following issues describe some of the most relevant challenges a designer should take into account. These issues are meant as a first approximation to a set of future design guidelines.

FOCUS ON SPECIFIC BARRIERS AND CONTEXTS

The lack of system visioning might lead to maladjustments of device features with the local health staff and create an idea of “charity design” and universal design that is now proved to be an inadequate approach.

The focus of designing medical devices should also not be on determined countries but rather on specific barriers. Developing countries have different health policies and governments. Countries such as Kenya or India do have high quality operating rooms, which serve only of a small percentage of the population. In the broad sense of view the largest barriers are also the long-term solutions. Transportation and road infrastructure, political

(democratic) stability and a fair expenditure in health and a culture of administration have still a long way to run.

USE CONTEXTUAL AND LIFE-CYCLE APPROACHES

The impact of the designed products should be placed in its full context and time frame. The consideration for all life-cycle phases of medical equipment allows the designer to understand the complete impact of a device in its context and make thus decisions based on the sustainability of the product or service and value of that impact: from pre-manufacturing, manufacturing, distribution, use, repair and finally disposal. Medical device innovation for these contexts can also have an impact in developed countries (e.g. Intraosseous transfusions by VidaCare) (Reddy et al. 2011).

MEET THE USERS AND THE CHOOSERS

Practitioners have preferences that allow them to perform with just the right level of confidence. Their preconceived ideas about a certain brand or technology have a significant weight on what determines the selection of certain medical equipment. Choice criteria are variable and unclear. Amongst many: the supplier's capacities (e.g. specification conformity, prices, experience and stock availability), manufacturer's service contracts and take back systems. More efforts should be made to clarify and discuss the discrepancy between perceptions of added value to surgical devices.

MINIMIZE IMPACT AND MAXIMIZE TECHNOLOGY POTENTIAL

Ideally with less impact and increased adequacy, the existing technology can promote leapfrogging in developing countries in order to achieve a global healthcare of quality and equality.

Context limitations to implementation of minimal invasive surgery (MIS) technologies involve e.g. demand of more experience with high-tech handling, is limited to diagnosis of abdominal emergencies and uses specific energy intensive and expensive equipment and its peripheral devices (trocars, monitor, dedicated illumination). Although there are on-going promising projects related with MIS and telemedicine, such as laparoscopic instruments that allow non-sterile environments, tele-controlled

surgical robots and remote training programs, these present still too many challenges to be considered in the scope of this project. Another issue of technology is that it might become a burden when it is dependent on human work/vigilance or on other technologies.

QUESTION THE STANDARDS, RESEARCH LOCAL CAPACITY

Policies and regulations are established among organizations so that the practice can be moderated from common practices and improved in future experiences. The state of the art though is that there is few shared knowledge about general humanitarian practices, reasons for which do not belong in the scope on this text. By recognizing that the work of humanitarian aid is performed in extreme settings it is possible to assume that the common standards applied to performance and devices must be properly adjusted if they are to defy the chances of people with life-threatening conditions. Research prior to development of products is fundamental to address cases in which standards "demanded" to devices are not well adjusted or do not have exceptions to extreme contexts. A reflection must be made whether new standards and regulatory guidelines to an existing device or a new device must be designed. The recognition of these platforms is fundamental from the initial stage of development since they regulate what is (and not) implemented in the market. Furthermore, it contributes for the optimization of sub systems between devices - a device is rarely stand alone.

Two projects of reference that contribute to health standards adequacy: 1)The Global Harmonization Task Force, who promotes the international consensus in regulatory requirements and practices that support new technologies, facilitate international trade and endorse worldwide safety and quality of medical devices and 2) the Sphere project that establishes context adequate standards for humanitarian assistance.

ADDRESS PRODUCT AND ITS ASSOCIATED KNOWLEDGE

Resources can be transferred by direct acquisition from recipients, donation or deployment. With estimation that of all medical equipment in

developing countries about 50% is found lying idle, there is an inefficient or non-mediated communication between donors and recipients. Local requirements, number of staff, their capability and level of technical expertise is often unknown. Even local manufacturer representatives and equipment distributors, who may be expected to provide after-sales support, are bypassed. Problems related to equipment calibration and operation, purchase of consumables and availability of spare parts may transform the donated equipment into a liability, rather than an asset, adopted either due to politeness or administration incapacity (Lister 2004; Organization of Health Services Delivery 2000). Communication regulation and clarification can be achieved by systematic and easy reporting. In order to establish a two-way communication it is necessary to know (perhaps in the form of level indicators) the priorities and capacities of both ends.

INVOLVE ALL STAKEHOLDERS, IDENTIFY EXISTING GAPS IN INFORMATION ABOUT PRODUCT

Throughout all these phases, and due to the complexity and rigour implicated in surgical devices, there are many stakeholders involved with this equipment. From patients to health administrators, government entities to insurers and regulators and finally all physician and technicians who handle, repair and dispose devices and their supplies. All of them have an important role to play when it comes to determine the:

- Demand for technology;
- The services which should be integrated;
- How they will be distributed, used and repaired;
- What it means to be affordable and acceptable;

Using a triangulation approach for data collected through participative methods with all the mentioned stakeholders, a systematic understanding of the context can be explored and by determining certain compromises, adequate solutions can be found (Garmer et al. 2002).

CONCLUSIONS

This exploratory study is intended to contribute to the development of context adequate surgical

devices for emergencies in extreme contexts. It belongs to a PhD study aiming to answer the research questions “How can industrial design engineering practice contribute to the safety of emergency surgery response in austere settings?” and “Which surgical equipment and related services can be developed without compromising the current practice of professionals?”.

The presented work precedes an extensive on-going literature review that intends to 1) review the problems associated with specific surgical equipment (including the reporting capacity of the actors involved in the process) 2) analyse them in terms of barriers, and 3) propose a set of indicators for minimum standards to assure the performance of equipment in any context.

These two studies will be compiled in a set of guidelines destined to contribute to the methodological enrichment of design practice and to support the development of context adequate medical equipment.

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